

QUIZ**LAST NAME: SHAH****FIRST NAME: DIPEN****PROGRAM CODE: LLM****COURSE CODE: ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: Pr. CLEENEWERCK****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. Asking the right question is important because

- Aim of education is to memorise the subject and topic being answered.
- It should spark debate.
- Others are keen to know the answer on a topic.
- It develops critical imagination required for professionals and paves the way for further research and help understand the larger issue.¹**

2. An argument may need a warrant to

- Make an argument more acceptable to readers than an argument based on evidence.

¹ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 8th edition., Chicago guides to writing, editing, and publishing (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 18,22.

- establish the relevance of reason to claim in the argument, as warrant is a general principle to which reason and claim confirm to general conditions and consequences of a warrant.²
 - Give elaborate reasoning.
 - Convince readers of research argument, as they are likely to trust argument based on warrant more than anything else.
3. In non-academic documents, citation appears within text of the documents as full sentences or as clauses immediately after the proposition. Which, according to you, is a true example of citation clause:
- The ITC's findings of fact should not be overturned because they are supported by substantial evidence, defined by Corning Glass Works as "such relevant evidence as a reasonable mind might accept as adequate to support a conclusion," Corning Glass Works v. U.S. Int'l Trade Comm'n, 799 F.2d 1559,1566 (Fed.Cir.1986), which will not be reweighed by the Federal Circuit on appeal even if an alternative conclusion can be drawn, Tandon Corp. v. U.S. Int'l Trade Comm'n, 224 F.3d 1356 (Fed.Cir.2000).³
 - Some American jurisdictions place the burden of sustaining criminal defences on the accused.¹
 - In several jurisdictions, the defendant must even establish that a homicide was accidental.⁴ The authors point out that the use of affirmative defences may relieve the state of its duty.⁵
 - The ITC's findings of fact should not be overturned because they are supported by substantial evidence. Corning Glass Works v. U.S. Int'l Trade Comm'n, 799 F.2d 1559; Tandon Corp. v. U.S.Int'l Trade Comm'n 831 F.2d 1017, 1019 (Fed. Cir.1987).

² Ibid., 40.

³ Harvard Law Review Association, *THE BLUEBOOK: A Uniform System of Citation*, 19th ed. (Cambridge, Mass: Harvard Law Review Assoc, 2010), 5.

4. Which of the following statements are true for short citations like “*id*” and “*supra*”:
- “*Id*” and “*supra*” can be used interchangeably to refer to a variety of citations within a non-academic environment.
 - “*Id*” is less preferable for use than “*supra*” as the latter is more flexible and also includes a mechanism to exactly point to footnote in which citation can be found.
 - “*Id*” can be used in citation sentences and clause for any kind of authority including internal cross-references, while “*supra*” cannot be used to refer to internal cross-references.
 - “*Id*” is used when citing immediately preceding authority, if preceding authority is singular and only one; “*supra*” is used to refer legislative hearings; court hearings; books; pamphlets; treaties and international agreements but no used to refer to cases, statutes, constitutions except in extraordinary circumstances such as when name of authority is long.⁴
5. Which of the following are common errors needed to be rectified in a research paper?
- Brief background with important points
 - Evidence supporting result.
 - Lack of genuine causal connection, explanation of the mechanism behind the result while using the result, attributing human characteristics to lifeless objects and use of raw data.⁵
 - Scientific proof and converted data duly presented in a summarised form.

⁴ Ibid., 72,74.

⁵ EUCLID, “ACA-401 Coursepack Period 4” (EUCLID, 2015), 11–14.

6. Which of the following is true?

- Capitalise the word only when used as a title.⁶
- Always use numeric numbers and not the whole-number words.
- Punctuate bullet points which are a list of items and do not put punctuation like semicolon to the end of each point when bullet point is a complete sentence in its own rights.
- Use single quotation mark even when a quote is indented (i.e., not in line with the rest of the text).

7. Which of the following statements is plagiarism?

- Giving credit to the author of an idea.
- Citing the source.
- Not citing a source of information generally available in public domain.
- Having someone write a paper for you and putting your name on it.⁷

8. For writing Introduction and Conclusion following is true.

- An introduction moves from general to specific, but conclusion moves from specific to general. Both are written after the body of the essay is written.⁸
- An introduction moves from being specific to general, but the conclusion is reverse of it and moves from being general to specific.

⁶ Ibid., 102.

⁷ EUCLID, “ACA-401 Coursepack Period 1” (EUCLID 2015), 10.

⁸ Ibid., 4.

- However, introduction and conclusion should be written one after another and but after the body of text.
- After knowing the thesis statement and gathering facts and analysing them, an introduction is written first followed by the conclusion. The body of the text is written after introduction and before the conclusion.
 - Introduction and conclusion are written first then followed by body of text.
9. **In thinking and writing your assignment the various acts of making connections and comparisons, organising information, making an educated guess, connect information, judging strengths and weaknesses and evaluating with clearness and accuracy are all parts of (select the correct corresponding order)**
- Evaluating, applying, understanding and recalling.
 - Recalling, synthesising, evaluating and analysing.
 - Analysis, applying learning, synthesis and evaluation.**⁹
 - Understanding, evaluating, synthesis and applying.
10. **KWL is a good study-reading strategy to use when you already know something about the topic. KWL stands for**
- ‘What I know’, ‘what I want to know’ and ‘what I learned’.**¹⁰
 - ‘What I know’, ‘where the information came from’ and ‘what is logic behind argument’.

⁹ Patrick Sebranek, Dave Kemper and Verne Meyer, WRITESOURCE A Guide to WRITING, THINKING and LEARNING (Wilmington, Massachusetts: Great Source Education Group, 2010), 290.

¹⁰ Ibid., 321.

- ‘What is the connection between facts’, ‘what is the connection of idea with the fact’ and ‘what we learned about the art of thinking’.
- ‘What I expect to know’, ‘what I know’ and ‘ what is the logic connecting fact to the argument’.

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